

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE NEWS PROGRAMS OF THE STATE AND PRIVATE TV CHANNELS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This scientific article covers the specific aspects of news media texts, and compares the main requirements for headlines and topics, shortcomings and achievements of information programs on state and non-state TV channels. What should be paid attention to in the selection of headlines and columns in state and non-state TV channels has been analyzed with the scientific works and opinions of leading experts in journalism. As research material, the reportage of the informational program of the "Yoshlar" TV channel "Yangi Davr" and the reportage of the informational show programs of the "Milliy" TV channel "Millar" on the same topic were analyzed.

Keywords: television, title, column, media text, genre, information, TV channels, informative programs.

Introduction. Today, although the journalistic style, the language and style of mass media have been formed, there are many issues that need to be studied in the language of television. The main task of mass media is united under the concept of "information". It follows from this that information programs are important to convey information correctly and to announce news to the public. "A news block is described in two forms: individual news clips and a complete news 'package'. Broadly speaking, the meaning of the word "news" is a set of periodical programs covering news or news. In the narrow sense, the term "news" is the clips that make up the content of informational programs, or more precisely, the clips related to news. [Струкова Е.В. Телевизионный новостной сюжет как разновидность медиатекста, 2008; 143–149].

Method.

In order to conduct research in this regard, we compared news programs on state and non-state TV channels. We received the program "Yangi Davr" from the state TV channel "Yoshlar" and the program "Millar" from the "Milliy" TV channel from the non-state TV channel. In this case, we received 3 consecutive broadcasts of each program. We compared socio-economic, spiritual-educational, and political news with the titles of topics covered in each issue of both TV channels. We analyzed the connection and structure of the blocks related to the interpretation of the given data, text structure and text psycholinguistics, sentence structure. interpretation of given information, text structure and text psycholinguistics, sentence structure.

Table 1

Titles of the "Yangi davr" program			
№	April 30	May 1	May 6
1.	Our players went to the Paris Olympics.	Today in our program	Forum of Central Asian Journalists
2.	Asian futsal championship.	A fair of products	"Boysun Spring"

		created by people with disabilities	International Folklore Festival has ended
3.	Plenary session of the lower house of parliament.	Constitution of Uzbekistan: achievements and priorities.	Can you tell when an earthquake will happen?
4.	UZB-Belarus cooperation in the education system.	Cooperation in the field of vocational education	Corruption is a social evil
5.	car accident caused by a school student	Malalla problems	Illegal drugs were seized
6.	Foreign News:	Fight against trafficking of psychotropic drugs	The number of victims reached 78 people
7.	Flooding in Kenya	Foreign News:	Ruang volcano became more active
8.	Tornadoes in the USA	The bus fell into a ravine	China is exploring the far side of the moon
9.	A 2,500-year-old helmet was found in Croatia	Tornadoes caused great damage	New opportunities for graduates
10.	Emperor penguins	A new species of dinosaur was discovered	In the house of a participant of the Second World War
11.		"Yosh oila.uz" platform	Presentation of projects focused on environmental problems
12.		Digital Technologies Forum	The Asian Championship has ended.
"Millar" program headlines			
№	April 30	May 1	May 6
13.	Why did the earth shake?	Briefly in our program today	Another terrible collision
14.	Graves without corpses	Three deaths in one household	Mother and child caught in flames
15.	Ways to play in Lazgi	Ice cream raid	Nervous kindergarten sister
16.	Car accident caused by students	He was imprisoned in a corrupt state	An 8-year-old girl was hit by a train
17.	Disputed debtors	The car thief was caught	The bus hit the barrier

18.	Guilty couriers	My 68-year-old slime	Officials caught with bribes
19.	Will the weather drop dramatically?	A man who wants to sell his kidney	Will the debtor be without a car?
20.		The debtor was arrested	Protect yourself from floods
21.		Do you know your rights?	The bus crashed
22.		Don't believe the false news!	Floods are rampant
23.		Decayed algae.	A terrible crime
24.		Saxophone thieves	Forum of Central Asian Journalists

News headlines and columns should be chosen based on the general content and direction of media texts. The headlines analyzed above are different from non-state TV channels with clear information delivery on state TV channels. Shomaksudova spoke about the originality of choosing a title, saying, "When choosing a title, you should be able to find a standard: it is not necessary to allow excessive originality or excessive repetitions." [Shomaksudova S.X. Mediamatn sarlavhasi retsiyent bilan samarali nutqiy kontakt o'rnatishning birlamchi vositasi."O'zbekiston xorijiy tillar ilmiy metodik elektron jurnal №1.2019]. We understand the exact content of the information from the headlines such as "China is exploring the back side of the moon", "Boysun Spring International Folklore Festival has ended" given on the state TV channel. However, titles such as "Terrible crime", "Rotten coals", "Dispute debtors" on the non-state television channel do not convey clear information. E.P. Prokhanov divides the text into 3 aspects as "important elements of information":

- value, that is, the value and importance of any given information for the audience
- "integrity", original information, information not out of date, titles not being the same
- the principle of decoding, that is, the understanding of information by the audience, understanding of the meaning inherent in the text. [Прохоров Е.П.Эффективность деятельности СМИ. – М.: Факультет журналистики МГУ, 2008 –46 с].

Table 2

№	"Millar" April 30	"yangi davr" April 30	Millar" May 1	Yangi davr" May 1	Millar" May 6	Yangi davr" May 6
Number of text blocks	9	6	7	7	7	7
Compound sentences	3	2	5	5	3	0
Simple things	8	15	5	15	33	12
Total number of sentences	11	17	10	20	36	12

Comparing each issue of the two programs reveals methodological inconsistencies and the same information is vaguely presented in the shows. For example, in the text of the following parts of the "Yangi Yur" program, there is a case of methodological insanity and a violation of logical consistency.

On social networks, "Namanganda school graduates were hit by a car.

The content of this sentence should have been incomplete, i.e. "such news spread in social networks".

In the following sentences, there is some confusion in the content of the text.

One of them died on the spot. Unfortunately, a student who came to Namangan from Khorezm region and was studying died due to the injuries he received.

From these statements, we can understand that the number of dead students is 2. Because in sentence 1 information is given about the student who died at the scene of the incident, in sentence 2 we understand that another student from Khorezm region passed away. Since this is the information in the first part of the report, 2 students have passed away or 1 will remain in this abstract form. In the next places of the text, we can understand that this is 1 student.

On April 20 of this year at 6:40 p.m., an 11th-grade student of school No. 57 in the district, born in 2007, living in New Namangan district, the "Lasetti" car, named after his uncle, was stolen on 7-Mingchinor street. drives, exceeds the set speed and goes to the opposite part of the road.

While the above sentence is considered a simple common sentence, the length of the sentence can lead to uncertainty in receiving information due to the abundance of information.

"On April 20 of this year, a boy who secretly left home in his toga car lost control and hit 2 students, one of them died on the spot, and the other got injured," given in the "Millar" program. In the information, it is said that the number of students is 3, and 2 students participated in the car accident in the "new era" program.

Conclusion. While publicist, official, scientific popular style is more used in the program of the state TV channel, we found elements of publicist, colloquial and artistic style more often in the private TV channel.

In the sentence structure of both programs, simple sentences are used more than compound sentences.

In the number of state and private TV channels we observed, industry terms and neologisms were not used

If we look at the topics of the columns of both programs, the state TV channels have information on various topics: social-political, foreign, cultural-educational, sports, art, and the information program of the private TV channel has social problems and news. developed.

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